

STUDY ON THERMAL PERFORMANCE OF GRANITE COMPOSITE FOR MACHINE TOOL STRUCTURES

HO-CHIAO CHUANG¹ and CHIH-RONG CHEN²

^{1,2} Graduate Institute of Manufacturing Technology, National Taipei University of Technology, 1, Sec. 3, Chung-Hsiao E. Rd., Taipei 10608 Taiwan. Email:wenlin57@gmail.com

Abstract

The structural support is a component that plays an extremely important role in the performance of the machine tool, as it must withstand the force and heat and suppress vibration to secure positioning without interfering with the function. The raw materials used in precision equipment must also have high rigidity, low density, high damping and high heat dissipation for maximum performance. Thus, in this study, Jinan black granite was used as aggregate, high-strength epoxy resin as adhesive and segmented carbon fiber as reinforcing material. The granites were crushed to a size less than 3.5mm to be used as the primary aggregate. High-strength epoxy resin would be used to glue the materials together. The entire compound was then reinforced by segmented carbon fibers. By mixing, stirring and casting, we obtained a test sample of size 100mm x100mm x 100mm. The test results showed that the maximum bending stress could reach 53Mpa. Its damping ratio was 6.5 times that of cast iron. The thermal conductivity coefficient was 1.2W/m.K and the thermal expansion coefficient was 1.4E-05 m/m.K, in which these physical properties have all demonstrated the material as a better choice than cast iron. The experimental results also showed that compared with cast iron, it could absorb vibration better and exhibited better properties in thermal conductivity and damping ratio, which showed it as a good reference for ultra-precision machining.

1. INTRODUCTION

Structural materials play a key role in the operation and performance of mechanical equipment. Therefore, the material must be selected for integrity and stability of functional equipment [1-3] and satisfy certain requirements, including strength, hardness, rigidity, heat resistance and corrosion resistance, as well as considering the cost of value and compatibility. Generally, cast iron, aluminum, composite materials and engineered polymers were used for structural support [1,4-6]. In modern concept of engineering, equipment must have characteristics compatible with the size of all parts [4,7], in order to maximize the distribution of space and weight of the apparatus in a working environment. The structural materials used in precision equipment must also have decreased component size and low level deformation caused by thermal exposure, especially when the damping of vibration was another characteristic worth mentioning for better performance in the manufacturing process [8-11], for which in small concept devices that this may become infeasible to design [7,12,13].

Polymers, such as the composite granites, have been widely used in the structure of machine tools, measuring equipment and medical analysis devices [15,16] since the mid-'70s [14]. Due to its high vibration absorption, it delivers excellent performance compared with ordinary materials. Artificial composite granites is advantageous in comparison because it allows the installation for fluid and rotating pipe as functional components in an apparatus; it can also use disposable industrial waste, making it a favorable characteristic with environmental and

economic benefits [15,17,18]. In this study, we proposed to improve the composite granites, in which it would be consisted of particles of $\varnothing \leq 3.5\text{mm}$ in size and glued together by epoxy resin for high mechanical strength. And, in some samples, we also used segmented carbon fibers for reinforcement.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Properties of materials

2.1.1. Jinan black granite

The mineral composite material in this study was mainly composed of Jinan black granite, adhesive and fillers, all structured as shown in Figure 1. in which, 01 is the fillers, 02 is the Jinan black granite and 03 is the adhesive.

The characteristics of the black granite in Jinan (see Table 1); the materials were from Huashan Town, Licheng District, Jinan City, Shandong Province, and China. Jinan black is the trade name of commercial granite. It is generally in block form, which must be first crushed and screened accordingly by particle size, typically as 0.2-0.4 mm (fine granularity); 0.4-0.6 mm (medium granularity); and 0.7-3.5 mm (coarse granularity).

Fig 1: granite copomsite material

Table 1. Physical properties of granite of jinan

Physics [↵] Propertie	Compressive [↵] Strength(MPa) [↵]	Flexural [↵] Strength(MPa) [↵]	Water [↵] Absorption(%) [↵]	Density [↵] (kg/m ³) [↵]
Value [↵]	257.1 [↵]	36.1 [↵]	12 [↵]	3.07 [↵]

2.1.2 The adhesive

In addition to Bisphenol epoxy resin, the adhesive would also contain curing agent, toughening agent and diluting agent, in which the brand of Bisphenol epoxy resin was HEXION, model: EPON58005, with heat resistance and shock resistance, providing a viscosity of 2500P at 25 °C The curing agent mainly regulated and promoted the curing reaction of epoxy resin; a necessary component to produce curing bonding. Some elements that require accelerated chemical reaction to cure, such as resin, will not harden into a solid state without a curing agent. In this study, Triethylenetetramine was used as the curing agent; it is a moderately viscous

yellow liquid with strong alkalinity with a density of 0.98g/mL, boiling point at 266°C and freezing point of 12°C at 25°C. Supplier of the agent was Guangdong Mingtu Chemical Co., Ltd. The diluting agent helped to reduce the viscosity of epoxy resin and increase its fluidity, allowing epoxy resin to penetrate layers of granite and fillers more easily, which further prolonged the curing time to achieve a better binding effect [19]. The main function of the toughening agent was to improve the ductility of epoxy resin and prevent its fracture under impact due to its inherent properties of brittleness [20-21]. In this study, Benzyl butyl phthalate was used as the toughening agent to increase the ductility and impact resistance of the mineral composite. Supplier of the agent was Nan Ya Plastics Co., Ltd.

2.1.3 Fillers

In the granite composite material, adding proper filler can reduce the amount of resin, reduce the cost, improve the dimensional stability and increase the mechanical strength by eliminating the curing stress [22] in the process of molding and mixing, preventing cracks and voids, and increasing the service life. In this study, A1203 and calcium carbonate were used as the fillers, and they showed the characteristics of slow heat transfer at room temperature but a high heat transfer coefficient at high temperature, which should improve the thermal conductivity of granite composite [23-24].

2.1.4 Reinforcement materials

Both carbon fiber and glass fiber can enhance the strength and toughness of the mineral composite, even though carbon fiber shows better result. The damping ratio of mineral composite will increase with the increase of fibrous component, because these fibers will increase the internal voids of the mineral material, leading to higher damping ratio. This study would use 1.7% carbon fiber as fillers [25-26]. For the synthetic granite composite reinforced with carbon fibers manufacturing, the proportion between the granulations of stones was maintained. Only 1.7% by volume of carbon fibers of 2.5 mm in length was added to composition A, fiber-reinforced composition being referred to as composition B. Figure 2 shows the optical microscope image of a synthetic granite composite polished section in (a) of composition A and in (b) of composition B.

Figure 2: Polished section images. Unreinforced composition (a). Reinforced composition (b).

The granite stones processing generates jagged gravel and it favors the morphological fixation between gravel and the other components used in the composite formulations. The Figure 2 shows all the medium and fine gravel fills the spaces between the coarse ones, also it is possible to observe the irregular gravel surface that favors composite phase's anchorage. There was no sign of chemical fixing, as envisaged by literature [27-28], between the material phases.

With the defined composition A of the synthetic granite, the specimens geometries were chosen for each test according to adequate standards and were performed specimens for tensile, flexural, compression, dilatometry, hardness, thermal conductivity and damping tests. For comparison with focused material of this study, aluminum and cast iron test specimens were also made for the damping test. Figure 3 shows the test specimens used.

Figure 3: Test specimens. 6161 aluminum damping (a). Gray iron damping (b). Synthetic granite damping (c). Thermal conductivity (d). Tensile (e). Flexural (f). Compression (g). Microhardness (h). Thermal expansion (i).

2.2 Laboratory equipment

For the mechanical strength tests a universal machine was used, model Bionix brand MTS®, with load cell of 15 kN. The tensile test followed ASTM D4762 [29], with a test speed of 0.07 mm/min. The flexural test followed ASTM D7264 [30], with a test speed of 0.1 mm/min. The compression test followed ASTM E2954 [31], with a test speed of 0.2 mm/min. were produced 10 specimens for each mechanical strength test based on standards used.

To measure the material thermal expansion coefficient, was used equipment DIL 402 C from the manufacturer Netzsch, were tested 10 specimens, according to ASTM E228 [32] with a heating rate of 2 °C/min. In the hardness test, a Leica micro hardness equipment, model VMHT MOT was used for Knoop hardness measurement from the application of a load of 200 grams, to measure the hardness 5 specimens were produced and 10 measurements were taken on each specimen following ASTM E384 [33] recommendations. The equipment used allows the precise visualization of the chosen point for indentation, hence it was possible choose points in the resin phase and in the gravel phase. For the hardness measurement, due to the material nature, it was decided to perform measurements for the different phases, since such information may be required, but for the other properties the measurements were made considering the composite as a whole, in order to obtain better data to be used in projects with the material being studied. The apparatus for measuring the material thermal conductivity was made with a thermal conductivity measurer of Hukseflux model TP-08 and a MINIPA® power supply

model MPL-1303, were used 5 specimens. The data acquisition system and test procedure was based on the Standard ASTM D5930 [28]. The vibration damping test was performed with cylindrical specimens of 6061 aluminum, gray cast iron and synthetic granite composite. The specimens were suspended by elastic attached to the ends. A PCB Piezotronics model 353B16 accelerometer was attached to one end of the test body. The impulse was applied through the PCB Piezotronics model 086C03 impact hammer. The acquisition system used was Data Physics Quattro®. The damping coefficient (ξ) was calculated by the logarithmic decrement method according to equation (1).

$$\xi = \frac{\frac{1}{n-1} \left(\ln \frac{x_1}{x_n} \right)}{\sqrt{4\pi^2 + \left[\frac{1}{n-1} \left(\ln \frac{x_1}{x_n} \right) \right]^2}} \quad (1)$$

To use equation (1) we choose two peaks x_1 and x_n separated by $(n-1)$ periods in the acceleration amplitude plot, plotted based on the accelerometer data.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Graphs of Average Tensions in the Tensile, Compressive and Flexural Tests

Figure 4: Average tensile (a), compressive (b) unreinforced flexural (c) results

Composition A showed tensile and compression strengths gain of about 80% and 30% respectively compared to traditional synthetic granites formulations of literature [27]. This improvement was due to the use of a high strength resin which had a strong impact on the improvement of tensile strength however lesser capacity to increase the compressive strength compared to the traditional resins used in this class of composites [27, 35]. The material reached tensile strength lower than pure epoxy resin and also was observed trans granular fracture on specimens of tensile tests, suggesting that for traction the polymer phase is the main responsible for the mechanical resistance. The results of tensile, compression and bending strength obtained are important in the evaluation of this material for use in mechanical structures. The damping coefficient is the major highlight of the synthetic granite, it was

measured in vibration tests through the response of an accelerometer adhered at the end of the bars that were subjected to an impulse. Figure 5 shows the decay graphs of the amplitude by time: The damping coefficient values by the Logarithmic Decrement Method [36] calculated for the three materials are shown in Table 2:

Figure 5: Amplitude variation of acceleration in time. Aluminum alloy 6061 (a). Grey cast iron (b). Synthetic granite (c).

Table 2: Damping coefficient

MATERIAL	$\bar{\xi}$	Standard deviation
Synthetic granite	0.0181	0.0019
Aluminum 6061	0.0033	0.0005
Grey cast iron	0.0029	0.0004

The produced synthetic granite composite presented excellent average damping coefficient, 5.5 times greater than aluminum 6061 and 6.2 times greater than gray cast iron, two materials

usually used in machine structures and precision equipment. These measured values of aluminum damping coefficient and cast iron damping coefficient are in agreement of literature [37-39], as well the damping coefficient measured by the granite composition [40]. These results show the advantage of synthetic granite for the vibrations absorption in mechanical structures, compared to metals traditionally used for this purpose, inciting its application in structures of machine tools and measurement machines. In the dilatometry test, an average expansion of $1.4E-5$ (m/m.K) was observed at working range temperature between 25 °C and 80 °C, lower than that found in commercial aluminum alloys that are around $2.3E-5$ (m/m.K) [and higher than gray cast irons ranging from $0.8E-5$ to $1.2E-5$ (m/m.K) [41,43]. Smaller values mean greater dimensional stability due to thermal variation so synthetic granite presents intermediate behavior between the considered materials. Therefore the measured value of the thermal expansion coefficient of the composite studied in the present work is satisfactory because it is within the thermal expansion coefficients range of metals commonly used for machine structures. The Figure 6 graph shows the behavior of thermal expansion coefficient in the temperature range tested.

Figure 6: Thermal expansion composition A.

Hardness is an important property for specific applications because a body supported on the structure receives loads which can result in high stresses. In this sense Knoop micro hardness tests were performed and the results showed a great variation in the measurements due to the hardness of the material phases present in the cutting surface: resin and granite (quartz and feldspar). The hardness in the areas of resin presented values in the range between 25 HK and 45 HK, in the stone areas in the range between 120 HK and 360 HK in agreement of literature [27,44]. For aluminum alloys and gray cast iron (class 20-40) the hardness is in the range of 88 HK and 170 – 260 HK, respectively [41,44], therefore, in relation to hardness the behavior of synthetic granite developed can be considered as an intermediate and consequently suitable for machine structures manufacture. Excessive heat concentration can generate local deformations in machine structure and must be considered by design. The structural material must have suitable heat conduction coefficient to avoid thermal distortions. The results of conductivity were 1.2 ± 0.1 W/m.K for the synthetic granite composition tested, lower than general metals alloys, (generally over then 10 W/m.K) [, although still higher than general polymers (commonly less than 0,7 W/m.K) and some types of composites [41-42]. Then for regions of machine structures made of synthetic granite where it is necessary to receive and dissipate heat quickly by conduction, a possible solution would be the use of metallic inserts. Composition B

was tested in a flexural test to evaluate the gain in mechanical strength with carbon fibers addition. The resulting graph of the bending tests of composition B is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Average flexural reinforced result composition B

It was observed 51 ± 2 MPa average flexural strength of composition B with gain of 20% relative to composition A, due to the reinforcement of the carbon fibers tests with larger fibers and with a higher concentration of fibers were made and presented increase in the mechanical strength, however the increase in the proportion or length of the fibers impaired the packing, requiring the increase of the resin proportion and for this work it was chosen to maintain the proportion of resin in the material for both composition A and composition B. The synthetic granite developed, made and tested in the present work presented the properties shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Properties summary

	μ (g/cm ³)	σ_t (MPa)	σ_c (MPa)	σ_f (MPa)	α (m/m.K)	HK	k (W/m.K)	ξ
Synthetic granite	2.1	27 ± 3	103 ± 5	42 ± 2 $*51 \pm 2$	$1.4 \text{ E-}05$	25 ~ 360	1.2 ± 0.1	0.018 ± 0.002

*Composition B.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Synthetic granite composite presents itself as a valuable alternative for precision machine structures manufacturing and has been explored since the 1970s. However, with the evolution of commercial epoxy resins and the introduction of carbon fiber, it was demonstrated in this work the possibility of a gain of up to 70% in flexural strength compared to traditional literature compositions. The developed composition showed remarkable ease of manufacture and enormous vibration damping capacity, among other good properties as a structural material.

With the composition of synthetic granite composite developed and tested its capacity is renewed for use in precision equipment structures with highlight to design concepts and prototypes. With respect to sustainability and depending on the granulometry of the grave used, these can be taken advantage of the immense ornamental stone industry waste and additionally the carbon fibers, in the length used, can also be obtained from composite industry leftovers, so that more than 80% of the material mass of the present work can be obtained as disposal material of other industrial processes and still with low energy consumption.

Reference

1. ASHBY, M. F., *Materials Selection in Mechanical Design*, 3 ed., London, Butterworth Heinemann, 2005.
2. LIANG, Y., CHEN, W., SUN, Y., et al., "A mechanical structure-based design method and its implementation on a fly-cutting machine tool design", *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, v. 70, n. 9, pp. 1915-1921, Nov. 2013. DOI 10.1007/s00170-013-5436-5
3. LUCISANO, S., MILADIN, S., FRAGASSA, C., "Advanced design solutions for high-precision woodworking machines", *International Journal for Quality Research*, v. 10, n. 1, pp. 143-158, 2016. DOI:10.18421/IJQR10.01-07
4. THE ROYAL ACADEMY OF ENGINEERING, *Philosophy of Engineering*, 1 ed., London, 2010.
5. DEHGHAN-MANSHADI, B., MAHMUDI, H., ABEDIAN, A., et al., "A novel method for materials selection in mechanical design: Combination of non-linear normalization and a modified digital logic method", *Materials and design*, v. 28, n. 1, pp. 8-15, Aug. 2005. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2005.06.023>
6. EDDY, D., KRISHNAMURTY, S., GROSSE, I., et al., "A Robust Surrogate Modeling Approach for Material Selection in Sustainable Design of Products", In: *Proceedings of the ASME 2014 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences & Computers and Information in Engineering Conference*, pp. 1-18, Buffalo, Aug. 2014.
7. MEHRABI, M. G., ULSOY, A. G., KOREN, Y., "Reconfigurable manufacturing systems: key to future manufacturing", *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, v. 11, n. 4, pp. 403-419, 2000. <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1023/A:1008930403506.pdf>
8. PIRATELLI-FILHO, A., LEVI-NETO, F., "Behavior of composite granite-epoxy bars subjected to mechanical vibrations", In: *VI National Congress of Mechanical Engineering*, Campina Grande, Aug. 2010. <https://www.scielo.br/j/mr/a/LxgqhRtCVJPXbgL7xBjr5JB/?lang=en&format=pdf>
9. KAMATH, S., D'MELLO, J., BALAKRISHNA, S. S., "Experimental study on mechanical properties os red granite-epoxy particulate composites", *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics Research*, v. 3, n. 4, pp. 178-187, Oct. 2014. <http://www.ijmerr.com/uploadfile/2015/0409/20150409113014336.pdf>
10. AGGOGERI, F., BORBONI, A., MERLO, A., et al., "Vibration Damping Analysis of Lightweight Structures in Machine Tools", *Preprints*, v. 1, pp. 1-14, Dec. 2016. file:///C:/Users/USER/Desktop/materials-10-00297.pdf
11. ERGUIA, J., URIARTE, L., LAMIKIZ, A., "Analysis, optimization and accuracy assessment of special-purpose portable machines by virtual techniques", *International Journal of Machine Tools & Manufacture*, v. 111, n. 1, pp. 31-42, Sep. 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmachtools.2016.09.006>
12. PARUCKER, M. L., KLEIN, A. N., BINDER, R., "Development of sintered nickel alloy by powder injection molding", *Matéria*, v. 19, n. 3, pp. 218-227, Sep. 2014. <https://www.scielo.br/j/rmat/a/qHmT7spx56VXtNDp95whJtv/?format=pdf&lang=pt>
13. BIKAS, H., STAVROPOULOS, P., CHRYSOLOURIS, G., "Additive manufacturing methods and modeling approaches: A critical review", *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, v. 83, n. 4, pp. 389-406, Jul. 2015. DOI 10.1007/s00170-015-7576-2
14. SERVO, J. C. P., *Seleção de um material alternativo para a estrutura de máquinas-ferramentas de arranque de apara*, Dissertation M.Sc., Minho University, Braga, Portugal, 2013.

15. RAMOS, D. T. L., PALLONE, E. M. J. A., PURQUERIO, B. M., et al., "Design and construction of a pin-on-disc bench for wear testing", *Cerâmica*, v. 60, n. 355, pp. 443-448, Jul. 2014. DOI:10.1590/S0366-69132014000300018
16. MURUGAN, S., THYLA, P. R., "Investigation on Dynamic Analysis of VMC Bed using epoxy Composite", *Carbon - Science and Technology*, v. 7, n. 4, pp. 66-75, Dec. 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1464420719840592>
17. [SOUZA, L. G. M., SANTOS, N. R., CAVALCANTE, A. A., et al., "Composite utilizing residues of marble and granite for building popular homes", *Jornal of Building Engineering*, v. 9, n. 1, pp. 192-197, Jan. 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2017.01.003>
18. GONÇALVES, J. A. V., CAMPOS, D. A. T., OLIVEIRA, G. J., et al., "Mechanical Properties of Epoxy Resin Based on Granite Stone Powder from the Sergipe Fold-and-Thrust Belt Composites", *Materials Research*, v. 17, n. 4, pp. 878-887, Aug. 2014. DOI: 10.1590/S1516-14392014005000100
19. Diaconescu R M, Barbula M, Harja M, Prediccion of properties of polymer concrete composite with line rubber using neural networks[J]*Materials Science &Engineering B*,2013,178(19).pp.1257-1267. Doi.org/10.1016/j.mseb.2013.01.014
20. Xu ping, SHEN Jiaying, YU Ying,et al.Study on damping properties of basalt fiber reinforced concreted, *Nonmetallic Mines*,2017,40(1):pp.30-32. DOI : 10.2991/emcpe-16.2016.120
21. Mukherjee A, Arwikar S J, Performance of Externally Bonded GFRP Steels on Concrete in Tropical Envinontures,2007,81(1):pp.21-33. Doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2006.05.013
22. Yao Binghua, Li Dexin Ying Jinch et al., UnStudy of Artificial Granite Composites and its Application *Materials For Mechanical Engineering*.1993,17(4):pp.37-39. www.soolun.com/periodical/79296556eef21e72ba182f469f040198.html
23. Hannawi K, Bian H, Prince A W et al., Effect of different types of fibers on the micro structure and the mechanical behavior of ultra-high performance fiber-Reinforced concretes, *Composites Parts B: Engineering*, 2016,86:pp.214-220. Doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2015.09.059
24. Fung K L, Li Robert K Y, Mechanical Properties of Short Class Fiber Reinforced and Functionalized Rubber-Toughened PET Blends, *Polymer Testing*,2006,25:pp.923-931. DOI: 10.1016/j.polymertesting.2006.05.013
25. Varughese K T, Chaturvedi B.K, Fly Ash as Fine a Aggregate in Polyester Based Polymer Concrete[J].*Cement Concrete Composite*,1996,18:pp.105-108. Doi.org/10.1016/0958-9465(95)00006-2
26. Černý R, Poděbradská J, Totová M, et al., Hygro-thermal Properties of Glass fiber Reinforced Cements Subjected to Elevelted Temperature, *Scientific Report*,2004,37(9):pp.596-608. Doi.org/10.1007/BF02483289
27. KAMATH, S., D'MELLO, J., BALAKRISHNA, S. S., "Experimental study on mechanical properties os red granite-epoxy particulate composites", *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics Research*, v. 3, n. 4, pp. 178-187, Oct. 2014 <http://www.ijmerr.com/uploadfile/2015/0409/20150409113014336.pdf>
28. GONÇALVES, J. A. V., CAMPOS, D. A. T., OLIVEIRA, G. J., et al., "Mechanical Properties of Epoxy Resin Based on Granite Stone Powder from the Sergipe Fold-and-Thrust Belt Composites", *Materials Research*, v. 17, n. 4, pp. 878-887, Aug. 2014 DOI: 10.1590/S1516-14392014005000100
29. AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR TESTING AND MATERIALS. ASTM D4762: "Standard guide for testing polymer matrix composite". West Conshohocken, 2016. <http://iccm-central.org/Proceedings/ICCM12proceedings/site/papers/pap1030.pdf>

30. AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR TESTING AND MATERIALS. ASTM D7264: "Standard test method for flexural properties of polymer matrix composite materials". West Conshohocken, 2015.
31. AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR TESTING AND MATERIALS. ASTM E2954: "Standard test method for axial compression test of reinforced plastic and polymer matrix composite vertical members". West Conshohocken, 2015.
32. AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR TESTING AND MATERIALS. ASTM E228: "Standard test method for linear thermal expansion of solid materials with a push". West Conshohocken, 2016.
33. AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR TESTING AND MATERIALS. ASTM E384: "Standard test method for microindentation hardness of materials". West Conshohocken, 2016.
34. AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR TESTING AND MATERIALS. ASTM D5930: "Standard test method for thermal conductivity of plastics by means of a transient". West Conshohocken, 2016.
35. RAMOS, D. T. L., PALLONE, E. M. J. A., PURQUERIO, B. M., et al., "Design and construction of a pin-on-disc bench for wear testing", *Cerâmica*, v. 60, n. 355, pp. 443-448, Jul. 2014. DOI: 10.1590/S0366-69132014000300018
36. OGATA, K., *Modern Control Engineering*, 5 ed., Upper Saddle River, Pearson, 2009.
37. [37] FRANCESCHINI, J. GOMES, H. M., "Avaliação de amortecimento estrutural usando-se o método do Random Decrement", *Engenharia Estudo e Pesquisa*, v. 10, n. 1, pp. 39-48, Jan. 2010. DOI:10.5281/7052056,10.5281/7052055
38. MAHENDRAKUMAR, N., SYATHABUTHAKEER, S., MOHANRAM P., "Study of alternative structural materials for machine tools", In: XXVI All India Manufacturing Technology, Design and Research Conference, Guwahati, Dec. 2014. <https://www.iitg.ac.in/aimtdr2014/PROCEEDINGS/papers/645.pdf>
39. SUBRAHMANYASWAMY, S., SREEDHAR, B. R., CHANDAN, K. M., et al., "Influence of resin content and cast iron powder addition on vibration characteristics of granite epoxy composites", *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science*, v. 3, n. 7, pp. 14578-14588, Jul. 2014. file:///C:/Users/USER/Desktop/48_Influence_2.pdf
40. SELVAKUMAR, K., GANESAN, K., MOHANRAM, P. V., "Dynamic analysis on fabricated mineral cast lathe bed", *Journal of Engineering Manufacture*, v. 227, n. 2, pp. 261-266, Nov. 2012. DOI : 10.1177/0954405412467141
41. ASHBY, M. F., *Materials Selection in Mechanical Design*, 3 ed., London, Butterworth Heinemann, 2005 http://www.utc.fr/~hagegebe/UV/MQ12/CORRECTIONS_TD/%5BASHBY99%5D%20-20Materials%20Selection%20In%20Mechanical%20Design%20Ed.pdf
42. LUCISANO, S., MILADIN, S., FRAGASSA, C., "Advanced design solutions for high-precision woodworking machines", *International Journal for Quality Research*, v. 10, n. 1, pp. 143-158, 2016 DOI – 10.18421/IJQR10.01-07
43. HIBBELER, R. C., *Resistencia dos Materiais*, 5 ed., São Paulo, Pearson, 2004.
44. VLACK, L. H. V. *Materials for Engineering: Concepts and Applications*, 1 ed., Reading, Addison-Wesley, 1982. <https://mechanicalc.com/reference/engineering-materials>